

Effects of Adaptive Mathematics Lessons On Student Achievements

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Literature Review

This study examined 3-6th grade students' ability to tackle math, performance and representation. It is in response to adaptive mathematics standards, mathematics content standards and mathematics practice standards indicating the need for adaptive learning methods to enhance students' performance. The aim of instructional intervention is to supplement or replace current methods to enhance student proficiency and performance in math as adaptive teaching lessons are becoming central in mathematics(Vaughn, 2014). Adaptive math lessons enhance proficiency and is characterizes successful mathematics learning in a way that a student develops conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning and a productive disposition towards mathematics. Mathematically proficient behaviors such as careful reading and observation, understanding, model creation and conjecture making about strategies and solutions gained from adaptive math lessons. Students that lack mathematical proficiency try solving math problems without making sense out of its context.

This chapter exhaustively audits literature in mathematics teaching, critically examines and approaches the benchmark for examination results survey in the field. It also focuses on the two theories of cognitive theory of multimedia learning and cognitive load theory to help explain how adaptive mathematics lessons can aid in improving mathematics achievements. The chapter builds up the writing setting in the field by selected theory discourse applicable in the modern situations in the state-funded schools, patterns and changes in state schools and examination structure; Knowledge Space Hypothesis, The Online Intelligent Systems, and embracing options like theIntelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) with in-depth focus on cognitive load theory and

cognitive theory of multimedia adaptive learning in math grades 3-6. This dissertation supports adaptive math learning and approaches their effects on student performance.

Current Landscape of Education in American Public Schools

The training framework in state funded institutions was founded on the Horace Mann's Prussian processing plant training model of the late nineteenth century. Baroody and Dowker (2013) asserts that this model was predominantly useful throughout the twentieth century as graduates took fabricating jobs at companies without higher request aptitudes. Inventions and innovations, mechanical autonomy and computerization effected a great change that gave birth to emergence of information economy resulting in the transitions in the employment markets and the post-primary alumni educational desires.

Bruns and Luque (2014) acknowledge that the state-sponsored American training framework has survived these drastic changes for over 130 years and is the main reason for the adoption of adaptive learning lessons that are registering tremendous gains on student achievements in several fields including mathematics. This emanates from the skill gap the changes in industry expectations. Progressions in innovation, mechanical autonomy, and computerization have caused a move towards an information economy. The employment markets have changed drastically, so did the desires of what a secondary school or college alumni must know and have the capacity to do.

Important employment executions in the low level and mid-level occupations have been dependent on fundamental math aptitudes with end work specific goals. Burton, Brown and Johnson (2013) note that resources are have been invested in elementary school courses, vocations and specialized instructions with an aim to ensure students equip elementary school leavers with important basic mental abilities so that they become useful in their professions later

in their lives. This has been inspired by increasing number of graduate workers lacking foundational math abilities that enable them to perform better than expected.

The United States, in the global math and science student appraisals, has been lagging behind European and Asian nations and these deficiencies have been reported by scientists and Press in a number of countries over the last decade. Clark, Chiang, Silva, McConnel, Sonnenfeld, Erbe and Puma (2013) argue that International mathematics trends that the United States employ in the third to sixth grade in arithmetic and science direct the tests like the clockwork in several nations. New thorough learning gauges in math have been planned by instructive strategy creators have been prompted by disappointments in the expanding negative separations between different nations' students and the United States student accomplishment.

Traditional Mathematics Instructing in the United States

Practical and intelligible educational modules are critical as supported by Carbonneau, Marley and Selig (2013) who argue that what to instruct and how to go about it is concentration on mathematics instructing. Powerful instructional tools and methods ensure conveyance of educational programs. The conveyance guarantees that all student gatherings have the substance and aptitudes.

State-sponsored instructing in the United States has experienced accomplishment differences among different ethnic gatherings and this has warranted the calls by instruction organizations to change government funded programs on the basis of solitary objective with the aim of filling the accomplishment gap. Chen and Wu (2015) define the accomplishment gap as the achievement gap between the execution distinction between each ESEA subgroup, school and the statewide normal execution.

The *No Child Left Behind Act* and the race taken after by training reformers' top activities have put substantial accentuation on math, perusing guidelines and advanced customized learning models on the basis of personalization, advanced learning and innovation (Good et al., 2014). Cicconi (2014) contends that personal gadgets have been put under student controls as pre-schedule moves to help connect with learners by the use of computerized modes.

It is additionally realized that the United States has been falling behind numerous other European and Asian nations in global student appraisals in the zones of math and science. It has been basic over the previous decade for scientists and the well-known press to report the deficiencies in U.S. student accomplishment on numerous countries (Kerr, 2015). For instance, Pew Research reports that the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), a relative universal trial of arithmetic science and proficiency aptitudes, positioned the United States 38th among 71 nations in arithmetic, and just 24th in science. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), a 35 country gather that supporters PISA testing positioned the US 30th in arithmetic and nineteenth science (Desilver, 2017). Kerr (2016) announced in the Associated Press (AP) that the Trends in International Mathematics, which directs tests like clockwork in numerous nations, that the United States put tenth in fourth-grade science and eighth-grade arithmetic. Kerr additionally announced that American students put fourteenth in fourth-grade science on the TIMMS, behind Portugal and Kazakhstan. Boss disappointment and the expanding negative separation between American student accomplishment and students of different nations are the reasons that drove instructive strategy creators to plan new and more thorough learning gauges, particularly in math, which accordingly prompted the reception of normal center gauges by 46 states and District of Columbia in the United States.

Darling-Hammond (2015) provides evidence from the national assessment of educational progress indicating that only 23-38% of 3rd to 6th grade students' scores are capable in math. These indications imply that more extensive crevice in math among students in schools and effects advanced education. The interest for medicinal math is also imperative in universities. Students acquire advanced education with lack of basics in science and math. Erhel and Jamet (2013) add that colleges are addressing these shortfalls by offering therapeutic courses. More than half of junior college students end up taking less than one medical math course as a prerequisite for enrolling in school level courses. This is because elementary and subsequently secondary school graduates lack essential and fundamental variable math and number juggling skills. It has also been reported that lack of numerical abilities is one of the main reasons for student school dropout. Many authors including Yilmaz (2017) support the assertion that adaptive leaning through a quasi-experimental study of 1110 students in the United States for the period between 2014 and 2015. Yilmaz found out that the adaptive learning for mathematics had increased students achievements and identified significant differences between the two groups.

Reducing disappointment and dropout rates has become an important undertaking in colleges in the United States. There is therefore a requirement for proof-based creative projects and mediations in math in order to help enhance student aptitudes for school level prerequisites and school ingenuity rates. Ghitulescu (2013) argue that a mixed learning model has been proposed to effect forward movement of math guidelines and supplement learning conditions adequately with computer-based segment. Instructive framework has also moved from customary strategies to innovation-helped strategies. Innovation, software engineering and web-based progresses have empowered innovation devices usage in training and have changed classroom guideline viewpoints.

These issues imply considerable problems in math training in the United States. National Mathematics Advisory Panel specialists have seen the need to repair the weakened mathematics instruction in the United States and have outlined six issues that need attention (Yilmaz 2017). Many mathematics analysts additionally argue that notwithstanding practical, intelligible educational modules are additionally similarly critical (McNulty, 2013). That is, we should concentrate both on what the students are instructed and how the monitoring is conducted. This raises the subject of what powerful instructional devices and procedures must be executed to have the capacity to guarantee an exceedingly compelling conveyance of the educational programs.

The first issue raised is in the measures whereby there exists a range of scattered and redundant benchmarks meaning that educators need guideline on what is important. Nations with higher accomplishment rates give considerable attention to annually set guidelines and project that students will involve those in more profundity.

Another issue is in the educational programs. To build a strong establishment in math, educational programs in the elementary and middle grades of 3-6 must be radically revamped with an aim of readying students to take variable based math by 6th grade. American state funded instruction has for some time been experiencing differences of accomplishment among ethnic gatherings. Instruction organizations both at the government and state levels have made innumerable endeavors to change government funded instruction on account of a solitary objective: shutting the accomplishment hole (Yilmaz 2017). The U.S. Branch of Education characterizes the term achievement gap as the distinction in the execution between each ESEA subgroup, as characterized in this report; inside a taking part LEA or school and the statewide normal execution of the LEA's or State's most noteworthy accomplishing subgroups in

perusing/dialect expressions and arithmetic as measured by the evaluations required under the ESEA.

The third issue raised is in the graduation requirements by pointing out that increased necessities must line up with student accomplishments and readiness as gauged by end-exams.

Another issue is the reading materials, in that, American course books are very large and cover a wide range of themes that instructors cannot traverse the course readings together with lined tests without the help of reasonable arrangement. On top of that, these course books only address definitions and equations but hardly extend into the mechanics.

Instructing itself was also an issue raised as there was no agreement among the analysts on what great math educating is. More math content must be included in educator instructor readiness programs and plans. Less experienced math instructors with solid mentorship and expert advancement must also be bolstered by schools and locale.

Heiling and Jez (2014) state that there are several barriers to the comprehension of math among students as evidenced by high number of students that encounter uneasiness in math and educators are therefore forced to cover the learning materials rapidly since they are strapped for time and assets thereby lacking the capacity to investigate the delights of math in crucial ways (West,, 2015). Course readings are composed and weighed to meet educational module prerequisites. More students can therefore comprehend and acknowledge math if instructors are accorded more time and flexibility (Williams, 2013).

Tailored learning approaches call for formulation of strategies to meet student interests allowing the students to hold information for longer time frames. These approaches work well with math because most students do not like the subject since they do not see its importance in their lives. This is because contemporary mathematics taught in classes do not connect to

genuine realities in the lives of students. One way of changing this is specifically fitting the inquiries to singular intrigues in the lives of the students when showing troublesome and dynamic math ideas.

Standardized Testing and Accountability

Institutionalized testing and assessment have been used in the last decade in government-funded schools. This move has increased the number of schools and educators who feel compelled to instruct as opposed to actualizing credible lesson arrangements in a bid to make adapting more charming to students (Vaughn, 2014). The accomplishment hole among various student gatherings (given socioeconomics and instructive needs) urges instructors to discover innovative approaches to utilize information in basic leadership to advise their guideline and make it more focused on. Instructors are required to utilize developmental and between times appraisals like never before to always survey student abilities and learning. Commentators who contradict testing contend that the more concentrate on appraisals the fewer time educators have for direction.

Given the socioeconomic and instructive needs, the accomplishment hole among student groupings drive instructors to discover innovative approaches to utilize basic leadership information and act as guidelines and center of focus (Spring,2016). Instructors therefore utilize developmental and appraisals to survey student learning abilities. Commentators contradicting testing argue that more concentration on appraisals reduce educators' time for direction. Profitable time for instruction should not be lost at the expense of developmental information (Sung, 2013). As a counter-measure, subjective mentoring permits are coordinating appraisal into classroom direction.

Personalized Learning Initiative

This being an age of constrained budgets and overworked instructors, adaptive learning brings the spark into math classrooms by innovation of educational approaches. Instructional content and methods are customized to individual students to help guide and facilitate learning and concept mastering. The new style of learning is data-driven and takes a non-linear approach to instruction and is therefore able to track students' progress as well as teaching, adjusting its instructions accordingly and provides instructors with crucial data helping them be more effective.

Higher quality and faster student progression

Instructors dealing with expanding classes have limited time to attend to all students' individualized needs. A high number of students in a classroom mean that an instructor has an even wider spectrum of academic knowledge and skills and it can prove difficult to secure time to write a broad curriculum to address student needs and check in with every student to ensure that they fully understand the lesson (Vaughn, 2014). Adaptive learning ensures that teachers and students spend more time on computer software to address one-on-one and small grouping needs.

Adaptability to different abilities

Adaptive learning has brought important education innovations such as the ability to change instructions on the basis of student knowledge. Every student works with a program and the technology picks up on their mastering or struggles and therefore adjusts instructions in real-time. Learning is therefore optimized since the learning program can change its approach on an individual level ensuring that students master concepts before they proceed to more difficult material. This bolsters student performance (Vaughn, 2014). Yilmaz et al (2017) argues that this does not add any significant value to student educational achievements asserting that educational adaptability is driven by other actors outside technology.

Improves understanding

It is difficult to know whether students are following up on a lesson. Adaptive learning methods and paces are customized for each individual student improving their chances of truly understanding new academic concepts. Student performance is therefore boosted as a result.

Student engagement

K-12 students are 'digital natives' since today's commonplace technology is part of their lives. They are techno-savvy and may become engaged in lessons should they be given a chance to spend part of their class with computers with adaptive learning programs.

Different learning paces

Traditional learning methods ensured that students of varying abilities learned the same academic materials at the same pace regardless of whether they understood different subject areas differently. This makes it deny struggling students the extra instructor time they need while at the same time challenging high-achievers and gifted students. Adaptive learning technologies ensure real-time student answers analysis as the software adjusts instructions accordingly. Students are therefore able to work at different paces and achieve best possible academic outcomes.

One-on-one instruction time free up

Adaptive learning programs implemented in blended learning free up time for teachers to give learners one-on-one instruction. It also customizes presentation and pace of new material in addition to monitoring and analyzing student responses thereby giving instructors access to invaluable data. This gives teachers the insight into whether students are grasping new concepts or not and help determine particular students could benefit from one-on-one instruction. This can go on as that students work with computers and rotational model of blended learning.

Mixed learning is one of the emerging models that strengthen customized learning situations by mixing gathering and individual direction and encourages innovation through computerized educational module (Yue, Ogawa, Startk, Kim, 2014). It envelopes a large variety of instruments and practices including broad innovation utilization in classrooms and web-based and developmental evaluation utilization, versatile student programs, learning administration theories and a number of other innovative headways (Schweppe, &Rummer, 2014).

In mixed learning, a student learns through a web-based approach. It incorporates components of student control and learning in a regulated place away from home. Course or subject modalities are associated with learning background of the students. Mixed learning's definitive objective is customized learning for all students. Mixed learning is a formal instruction program in which a student learns, at any rate in part, through web-based learning. Mixed learning incorporates some component of student control after some time, place, way, or potentially pace and incorporates learning, in any event to some extent, in a regulated physical area far from home. The modalities inside a course or subject along every student's learning way are associated with give an incorporated learning background. Kupczynski and De Raedt (2016) and Varsavsky (2010) expressed that a definitive objective of mixed learning is customized learning for all students.

No Child left Behind Act of 2001 was unanimously passed by the congress of the United States to help close the accomplishment gaps in math and reading (Vinovskis, 2015). It has, with definitive objective of all students' ensured gains in sufficient annual meetings and capability. A number of schools are lagging in this goal-oriented objective. Specialists proposed mixed learning as an effective math accomplishment hole filling approach. Adopters have been registered throughout the years in various regions and schools all over the nation. An increasing

number of school executives are also executing distinctive curriculum activities in math lessons despite lack of exact research to show their efficiency.

The viewpoint is versatile learning programming effects on math accomplishments and how these advanced learning instruments help customized learning or low and middle (grade 3-6) school students.

Cognitive Load Theory in Adaptive Learning Technologies

Cognitive Load Theory and Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning are the applicable theoretical frameworks since they utilize multimedia support to student learning by featuring characters, animations, music, songs, color, narration, contextual art and videos. These two pivotal hypotheses frame the establishment of innovation in versatile learning. Cognitive Load Theory makes critical commitments to instructive innovation with focus in math. The second is the Adaptive Control through Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning. Learning space theory is applied in making misleading but clever versatile learning programming in math. Learning Space theory is an essential portrayal and depends on priority connection. Priority connection could be utilized to outline powerful and thorough evaluation instruments. This idea has changed the advanced learning market or math instructions.

The cognitive load theory is based on the premise that learners are able to absorb certain percentage of new information within a specified time. The theory discourages overloading students with information since their mental capacity is finite. Sweller (2016) insists that the working memory or the short term memory retains limited amount of information. The theory observes that learners have mental “schema” that aids in solving problems as well as aiding in thinking. Three forms of cognitive loads are identified in this theory that includes intrinsic, extraneous, and germane. The intrinsic cognitive load is the complexity inherently involved in

performing some tasks. When some activities of information are hard to learn, they are likely to cause intrinsic cognitive load. Extraneous load includes the non-relevant and unimportant elements that occupy the capacity of learners. The germane cognitive load contains the elements that help the person to learn the processes and facilitate development of the knowledge base. Sweller (2016) suggests approaches that can be embraced in reducing the cognitive overload in eLearning platforms. The approaches include keeping the information intended for learning simple and brief to the point. The author also suggests that tutors use different instructional techniques especially those that make learners participate during the study, and then making the learning process “bite size” to enable the learners comprehend the information provided.

Adaptive web-based programs are largely being used in manmade brainpower and psychological science. This hypothesis makes it easy to uncover the learning condition of specific students in specific math themes through online evaluation. The state of learning is characterized by the entire issue arrangement in a specific subject that a student can illuminate. This standard provides that shrewd versatile appraisal makes issues and ideas guiding students and instructors on action requirement and learning preparation of students. These two frameworks reveal an individual student finish learning condition under evaluation. Instructors are therefore able to survey the information condition of their students and figure out their qualities and shortcomings in order to tailor their lessons to meet the ever-changing student needs. Through this, educators are able to separate guidelines and tailor learning for each student improve student’s attitude towards math.

Herrington, Reeves and Oliver (2014) contend that Learning space hypothesis remolds the specialist instructor abilities to survey the conditions of learning of an student and inform an online student evaluation keeping it updated and accurate. All conceivable states of learning

identified with this point are contained in a specific math subject in an information space that maps out subtle elements of every student's information and gives directions if they are faced with perpetual appraisal circle. Adaptive learning programming recognizes what the students are prepared to learn next based on their renewed state of learning. It utilizes learning to give criticism to learners and make adapting more effective thereby giving consistent development ways by promoting students a choice of the subjects they are prepared to learn at a particular time. This therefore ensures a tailored condition of learning among the students in which every learner progresses at their own paces as though they are being examined by a private coach.

Cognitive Theory of Multinational Learning

The theory was developed by Richard Mayer and it is based on three assumptions that include the opinion that two separate channels exist for processing information including visual and auditory; that learning should be an active process involving stages of sieving, picking, organizing as finally integrating synthesized information. The third assumption is that the channel capacity is limited and thus should be provided with information supposed to be synthesized and comprehended. Mayer (2014) suggests that design principles of the theory includes providing adequate pictorial information, guiding the students to pick the relevant images and words, providing coherent verbal information as well as reducing the load for single processing channel since they are finite. Mayer (2014) contends that Knowledge space theory provides a system to formally portray learning structures and spaces. Conceivable learning arrangements are confined by essential connections between specific things and portray hypertext structures in which essential connections indicate hypertexts segments. These connections end up being very comparable making it conceivable to plan savvy hypertexts

coaching frameworks for individualized guideline through hypertext model blending with learning space hypothesis. The quality and proficiency of the versatile hypertext-based ITS can be derived from two things. The first one is the powerful strategies employed by learning space hypothesis in distinguishing structures in a given space of learning. Another is the hypertext portrayal display that utilizes scientific relations to interface essential connections to particular learning segments inside the student's information state.

Applying techniques for social database hypothesis to learning area structures concerns not only singular access to report fitting for student's genuine information but also the development of sub hypertexts because of instructive targets or to the student's earlier information (Yue, Bjork & Bjork, 2013).

Consolidating information space hypothesis with social hypertext demonstrate Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning model called RATH (Relational Adaptive Tutoring Hypertext). Basic likelihood hypothesis was picked as the underlying course to be fused into RATH as a learning area because of the way that numerous students had troubles with this course, subsequently promote instructional support was required. Some other math courses could be effortlessly included into RATH, given that a coaching hypertext is accessible containing lessons, illustrations, appraisals, and some other educating materials for the course. In spite of the fact that the underlying model of RATH was instrumental in giving instructional support to students, a few zones of change for RATH have been identified, for instance, the expansion of an underlying evaluation to decide a student's present information state as opposed to beginning everybody off with the presumption of zero information in the course, and enhancing investigation of student answers to work out inquiries with a specific end goal to give important input instead of simply giving a genuine/false reaction. The creators presume that RATH was an

imperative venturing stone for consolidating mental hypotheses into savvy coaching frameworks (Ramirez, Chang, Maloney, Levine & Beilock, 2016).

Learning space hypothesis as the foundational design of a probabilistic student model to be installed into an ITS. The scientists were especially intrigued by a probabilistic student demonstrate keeping in mind the end goal to have the capacity to speak to the instability of evaluating student learning. A few components add to vulnerability in student displaying, for example, imprudent mistakes and fortunate conjectures in the student's reactions, changes in the student information because of learning and overlooking, and examples of student reactions just unforeseen by the originator of the student show. Oakes, Lipton, Anderson and Stillman (2015) contend that in learning space hypothesis the fundamental unit of learning are characterized as a thing. Two fundamental strides are considered in the development of their probabilistic student demonstrate: fabricating the auxiliary connections among the things in spaces of learning, and deciding the underlying likelihood esteems in the models. Taking after these means required master judgments and additionally observational student information (Plass, Heidig, Hayward, Homer, & Um, 2014).

Summary of Literature Review

The chapter addresses the issues related to effects of adaptive math lessons on student achievement in mathematics in Grades 3-6. A section on the literature review handles information on the current landscape of education in American public schools with a focus on why adaptive learning approaches are needed. Traditional mathematics instructing in the US is explained with the focus on the need of embracing new approaches to teaching mathematics, as well as explaining briefly the provisions of the *No Child Left Behind Act* that defines equal opportunities for learners (Good et al., 2014). Important metrics like PISA are addressed and how they help in

assessing performance and achievements of students in mathematics. The literature also highlights the statistics on mathematics performance among the US students as compared to other nations, as well as providing some approaches that are better situated to improve mathematics achievements. Approaches of measuring achievements in mathematics in grades 3-6 including Standardized Testing and Accountability, personalized learning initiatives, and adaptive learning technologies. The chapter also highlights the two theories, cognitive load theory and cognitive theory of multimedia learning, that explain how adaptive learning technologies can enhance student achievement in mathematics in grades 3-6. The literature focuses on how the theories support adaptive mathematics lessons in improving student achievements.

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